

Doing AI Differently

Policy note

The
Alan Turing
Institute

This policy note summarises key recommendations from the Doing AI Differently white paper – an international research initiative that outlines how interpretive capabilities can be embedded into the foundations of AI development, from frontier models to domain-specific systems already in use.

The United Kingdom has declared its ambition to become a global AI superpower. The Modern Industrial Strategy places technology at the heart of the UK's future prosperity, and the AI Opportunities Action Plan provides a roadmap for this ambition. The success of this ambition hinges on overcoming a critical challenge: the implementation gap. This is the gap between an AI's performance on technical benchmarks and its effectiveness in real-world settings. As AI undergoes a 'qualitative turn' – becoming embedded in the fabric of our culture, language, and society – its success cannot be measured by technical performance alone. Overlooking the complex, interpretive, and deeply human context in which AI operates risks building a brittle and distrusted technological future, repeating the societal missteps of previous technological waves.

What is needed is interpretive depth: AI systems that can understand context, cultural nuance, and multiple valid perspectives – rather than producing single "correct" answers. The UK is doing excellent work in driving responsible AI in deployment, but building AI systems capable of interpretive depth requires humanities practitioners as co-designers upstream when these systems are designed and built. This capability is essential for performance and adoption in real-world deployments – from sustainability to healthcare – and for sovereign systems inclusive of and reflective of British culture, diversity and values.

Policy recommendations:

Recommendation 1: Develop and incorporate interpretive evaluation frameworks into public sector AI procurement.

The challenge: A primary cause of the high failure rate of government technology projects is that they are procured and evaluated against narrow, decontextualised technical benchmarks. An AI system may perform exceptionally well on a standardised test but fail when deployed in a real-world council or hospital.

Our proposal: Create interpretive evaluation frameworks for procurement, co-developed with domain experts and end-users, which assess an AI's performance in context.

Practical steps: The Government Digital Service should update the AI Playbook to include a chapter on interpretive evaluation for procurement. The government should mandate the use of interpretive evaluation frameworks for all high-value or high-risk public sector AI procurement.

Recommendation 2: Establish human-AI ensemble pilot programmes within national missions.

The challenge: The dominant paradigm for AI in industry and policy is one of automation leading to the replacement rather than augmentation of human labour and skills. This approach risks creating systems and processes that are powerful but lack judgment.

Our proposal: Establish pilots for human-AI ensembles. These are frameworks for sophisticated, collaborative human-AI systems that preserve human agency and support meaningful decision-making. Pilots should be targeted at high-priority government missions where interpretive depth is essential, such as healthcare systems that must navigate diverse patient narratives.

Practical steps: The government should designate a portion of AI Growth Zone funding to specifically pilot and champion human-AI ensemble systems. The new UK Sovereign AI unit should partner with a leading university located within or near a designated Growth Zone to launch a flagship pilot programme.

Recommendation 3: Establish interpretive AI assessment capability for foundation models as a direct policy workstream

The challenge: The government's focus on AI safety and security is crucial, but the current emphasis on headline risks like deepfakes, malicious use and model failures overlooks the subtle but pervasive risks that arise from an AI's interaction with complex human contexts. Simple technical benchmarks can be inadequate for evaluating performance on contested or ambiguous topics.

Our proposal: To build a truly robust and holistic safety regime, and a more comprehensive AI assurance ecosystem, the government should establish Interpretive AI Assessment as a core capability, developing and standardising methods to evaluate how AI systems handle ambiguity, cultural context, and diverse values.

Practical steps: Formally expand the remit of the AISI and extend the AI assurance roadmap to include Interpretive AI Assessment for the most advanced models.

Recommendation 4: Launch an interpretive AI leadership fellowship scheme to build cross-sector capacity

The challenge: The UK possesses world-class talent, infrastructure and knowledge in both technology and the humanities. However, there is a constant risk that these communities operate in silos.

Our proposal: The government should scale up a proven model to create a new cadre of boundary-spanning talent, enhancing cross-fertilisation of different modes of thinking about evidence, context, and meaning, enriching approaches to system design and policy development.

Practical steps: Harness the opportunities in this area by supercharging ongoing initiatives such as the Turing Pioneer Fellowships, the Spärck AI Scholarships, and the Arts & Humanities Research Council's BRAID programme.

Recommendation 5: The 'made smarter: interpretive AI' challenge for advanced manufacturing

The challenge: AI adoption in the manufacturing sector is hampered by the complexity and cost of implementation, as well as a significant knowledge gap among firms. An estimated 80% of a product's lifecycle environmental impact is determined during its design. Standard AI systems struggle to handle the complex, multi-faceted, and often interpretive trade-offs in design, balancing aesthetics, material properties, sustainability, manufacturability, and implicit user needs.

Our proposal: The government should launch a 'Made Smarter: Interpretive AI' Challenge, modelled on the Made Smarter Adoption programme which supports technology adoption in manufacturing small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and other existing national efforts such as the Smart Design Innovation Network's Augmented Design Practices programme. This fund would co-invest in collaborative R&D projects that develop and deploy human-AI design ensembles.

Practical steps: The Department for Business and Trade and Innovate UK should launch a pilot fund focused on this challenge, targeting the priority sectors of the Advanced Manufacturing Sector Plan, especially automotive agri-tech.

Recommendation 6: Incorporate doing AI differently principles into the deployment of the creative industries sector plan

The challenge: The UK's global leadership in the creative industries is built on experimentation, cultural expression, and nuance. AI deployed without interpretive depth risks de-skilling the workforce and homogenising creative output, undermining the very qualities that define the sector's success.

Our proposal: Prioritise projects that place cultural understanding, plurality, and meaning-making at the core of AI design.

Practical steps: UKRI should use Doing AI Differently principles into assessment criteria for its £100 million Creative Industries R&D investment. It should pilot human-AI ensemble systems in high-priority creative sectors. Working with the Creative Industries Council, it should establish ethical frameworks ensuring AI enhances rather than displaces creative workers.

Recommendation 7: Champion methodological innovation for effective AI development

The government's goal: The AI Opportunities Action Plan and the wider Industrial Strategy aim to accelerate innovation by working closely with academics and entrepreneurs. However, the implementation gap between AI ambition and successful execution is often a result of failing to integrate diverse forms of expertise early enough in the design process.

Our proposal: The government should incorporate 'humanities upstream' (integrating interpretive expertise in core AI development) and 'intentional field building' (creating the shared spaces, language, and goals needed for experts to solve problems together from the outset) into its strategy.

Practical steps: UKRI, in partnership with DSIT and the new Sovereign AI Unit, should launch a 'Methodological Innovation Challenge' as part of the AI Opportunities Action Plan's R&D funding. This would specifically promote projects that use 'humanities upstream' and 'intentional field building'.

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